

Systematic discovery of cell biologic and immune function in IBD: Interleukins.

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Interleukins

a. IL4i1

- i. Baseline partial reduction in CD NOD2 mutants
- ii. Activation in wild-type following MDP stimulation is lost in SNP13 homozygote but intact in SNP13 heterozygotes

b. IL-18

- i. Activated by MDP
- ii. Activation is lost in CD patient monocytes

Citations

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